

Automation and autocommunication: A typology of self-communication with wearables**Abstract**

Wearables increasingly intervene in human communication, including communication with the self. To better understand such processes, this article provides a typology of autocommunication as it relates to wearables. Building on Lomborg and Frandsen's (2016) conceptualization of self-tracking as communication with the self, and Lotman's (1990) concept of autocommunication, the article theorizes how communication with wearables become incorporated into people's inner communication, meaning-making, and decision-making processes. The analysis draws on 69 photo diaries and interviews with 25 users of wearables and identifies three interrelated dimensions of autocommunication: about the device, the data, and the body. Along these dimensions, people make decisions through internal interpretations of communicative messages from wearables, as part of their ongoing autocommunication. By conceptualizing wearables via the concept of autocommunication the article shows how the body remains the main point of reference for meaning-making against which interactions with wearables are continuously weighted, interpreted, and sometimes questioned.

Keywords: Autocommunication, bodily communication, personal decision-making, wearables, self-tracking, repair, maintenance, personal data

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Wearable digital tracking technologies are connecting and intertwining with human bodies, often to optimize the body or overcome bodily shortcomings (Van Den Berg, 2012). For instance, by collecting and analyzing data, wearables can enhance bodily organs to function normally for people with diabetes or heart disease, and they can help people optimize productivity levels, improving physical performance, sleep patterns, and the like. Wearables should therefore be understood broadly as encompassing devices carried with, on, or in the body to facilitate *mobile tracking, personalized decision-support, and connectivity* (Petersen & Iliadis, 2020). This broad definition includes smartphones that too are carried or worn in extension of the body and works through dedicated self-tracking apps or as central hubs for other wearables' functioning (e.g. an app pairing with a glucose monitor, a smartwatch or an Oura ring). The wide range of applications for wearable technologies in people's lives, and the fact that they are *wearable*, has led to concerns about a resulting disciplining of the self via biometric (self-)surveillance, even while recognizing their potential benefits (Sanders, 2017). In addition, imaginaries about technologies that enhance and possibly alter the human body typically center around speculations on whether human bodies are merging with machines, and around fears of the future impact of automation on humanity (Russell, 2019; Markoff, 2015). Such imaginaries often depict future scenarios with novel technologies as highly advanced, blackboxed, and difficult to comprehend, overestimating the powerfulness of technology while underestimating the human role in shaping technological futures via communicative practices (Scott Hansen, 2022). Indeed, technologies that datafy various aspects of humans are inextricably linked to human communication through the bodily inputs and interpretations of information. Through small everyday practices of *autocommunication*, people interpret

automated inputs from wearable technologies and incorporate them into processes of communicating and making decisions with and about themselves.

This article draws on longitudinal qualitative research to detail what autocommunication is and how it relates to wearables. *It asks how wearable devices that are used in everyday life for personalized decision-support intervene in human autocommunication.* In doing so, it extends Lomborg and Frandsen's (2016) conceptualization of self-tracking as communication with the self. Specifically, it returns to Lotman's (1990) original designation of communication with the self as autocommunication, which is mentioned in the context of self-tracking technology by Lomborg and Frandsen (2016) but not fully unpacked. This article further showcases the value of studying autocommunication in a new situation: wearable technologies have become integral in people's lives influencing how they communicate with themselves to make sense, choices, and decisions that shape who they are as individuals. Drawing on 69 photo diaries and interviews with 25 participants, I present a typology of autocommunication related to wearables and highlight how it operates through self-sustaining and self-inventing modes in internal dialogue, as identified in Lotman's work (Tamm, 2019). The article shows how autocommunication covers three dimensions when people use wearables: they communicate with themselves about the device, the data, and the body. Along these three dimensions, people engage in decision-making processes related to their wearable devices, their tracked data, and their bodily experiences. Conceptualizing wearables via the concept of autocommunication shows that, in relation to these dimensions, the body still works as the main point of reference for meaning-making against which interactions with wearables are continuously weighted, interpreted, and sometimes questioned.

The article first reviews the literature on selfhood as configured by wearables that enable and extend autocommunication in specific ways. It then introduces Lomborg and Frandsen's (2016) conceptualization of self-tracking as communication with the self as a

starting point for elaborating on Lotman's (1990) concept of autocommunication, including its self-sustaining and self-inventing modes. It then presents the typology of autocommunication, showing how communication with oneself is always about devices, data, as well as bodies when wearables are involved. Finally, it discusses how the abundance of data for personalized decision-support with wearables is tied, first and foremost, to bodily communication processes.

Selfhood and self-tracking with wearables

Research has explored different aspects of how the self is constructed with wearables in complex processes of humans communicating with themselves. One stream in the literature has described wearables as tools for automating data collection, suggesting that wearables optimize humans and their bodies by providing more data and more objective insights for better decisions and outcomes in developing the self. Such uses of wearables in shaping selfhood have often been associated with "The Quantified Self" movement and the "view of the body/self as a machine-like entity, with 'inputs' and 'outputs'" (Lupton, 2013, p. 26). Lupton (2016; 2020) describes the use of wearables for data collection as a strategy of selfhood that addresses the importance of self-reflection and self-improvement. Here, self-tracking technologies are often used to promote and create "'improved' modes of behavior" and proactivity, and structures everyday life through rhythmic and repetitive cycles of tracking things like moving, eating, and sleeping (Vigren & Bergroth, 2021, p. 137). As Lupton (2020) notes, individuals may thereby "[...] 'take charge' of their lives by regularly monitoring themselves" using wearables, and "the very act of self-tracking" thereby becomes "a profound act of selfhood and embodiment" (p. 84). Thus, wearables help individuals not just collect and keep data about their body; but also construct themselves as people *utilizing* data to understand their bodies and improve themselves, ultimately reinforcing the experience of being an improved, enhanced, optimized (Kristensen, 2022; Meißner, 2016) – or simply "better" version

of oneself (Lupton & Smith, 2018). However, despite being sold as “empowerment” tools, wearables do not *always* help users the way users had hoped they would (Neff & Nafus, 2016). The idea of self-optimization through self-tracking technologies in these contexts can be understood as “a set of discourses and practices that encourage individuals to pursue the optimal imaginable version of their bodies, their mental and emotional constitution, and their conduct of everyday life” (Nehring & Röcke, 2023, p. 2).

Studies in this stream have investigated how data present our bodies to us as entities that can be operated, steered, maintained, repaired, and optimized in specific ways (Pedersen & Iliadis, 2020) – but also how data-driven systems often need “user-repairers” to handle frequent technological failures (Forlano, 2017, p. 33). Wearables thus make claims on humans’ bodies to engage in certain practical tasks. In these cases, caring for technology often serves as a means for humans to care for themselves, because they rely on their devices and data to make their bodies or lives function (Wiedemann, 2021). In this sense, self-tracking becomes a practice of caring for and controlling or governing oneself at the same time (Krzeminska, 2024). In these perspectives, data contribute to the construction of a form of selfhood where “the task of the self is to calculate optimal choices that are dictated by evidence-based target levels” (Ruckenstein & Pantzar, 2017, p. 9). What is characteristic about this configuration of selfhood is that it takes its point of departure in a notion of “mechanical objectivity” (Pantzar & Ruckenstein, 2017). As Pantzar and Ruckenstein (2017) put it, “The framework of mechanical objectivity tends, however, to fall short when people translate physiological measurements to fit their expectations and everyday experiences” (p. 1). Instead, they develop a notion of “situated objectivity” to account for how data generated via digital tracking technologies should be understood relative to personal interpretations, reflections, and ambiguities that arise in the context of their everyday lives.

Another stream of self-tracking literature emphasizes how wearables can oppress users, sometimes passively through data-driven nudging (Schüll, 2016). This literature focuses on the construction of selfhood with wearables as imbued with an optimization regime and tied to broader power structures in a society, based on ideas of discipline and surveillance (Sanders, 2017). For instance, the intersection of selfhood with broader societal structures of power and discourse was famously described by Foucault (1986; 1988). From a Foucauldian perspective, societal power structures are internalized in individuals and implicitly push them to engage in self-surveillance with wearables. As Lupton (2016) points out, drawing on Foucault's theories (1986; 1988), the use of wearables can be understood as being part of a broader historical and cultural context of practicing the self, based on certain "ideas and discourses about how citizens should behave and conduct themselves" (Lupton, 2016, p. 46). For instance, research has shown how contemporary (big) data and data analytics imaginaries (e.g. Beer, 2019; Olbrich & Witjes, 2016; Rieder, 2018), which are "increasingly dominated by technology companies" (Mager & Katzenbach, 2021, p. 223), represent a wider societal submission to processes of "datafication, dataism and dataveillance" (Van Dijck, 2014). Recent data studies literature has further highlighted how such forms of power operate through the very configuration of data subjects by shaping what even counts as data about the body and self, and thereby how individuals come to be represented through quantification (Dalmer et al., 2024). In a previous study of the discursive underpinnings of self-tracking technologies for personal data analytics, Berg (2017) also shows how "[t]here is an assumption in these presentations that life in contemporary society is moving so fast that it is nearly impossible to trust one's senses and experiences. The body, as it seems, is simply too slow to keep up [...]" (p. 5). There is an "[...] imperative to control both the unpredictable nature of one's body and the data that are generated about oneself, and the valorizing of digital data" (Lupton, 2013, p. 29). While research indicates that accumulating personal data may not be easily translated into meaningful insights and lead

to better outcomes or decisions (Fors et al., 2020; Lomborg et al., 2020; Lomborg et al., 2018; Pink, Ruckenstein, Willim, 2016; Rapp & Cena, 2016), these data imaginaries seem to persist, in part because they are still repeatedly curated and circulated by pioneer communities such as the Quantified Self that position self-tracking as part of a desirable digital future (Hepp, 2025).

Foucault's (1988) concept of "technologies of the self" (p. 18) refers to products of these types of discourses and power structures in society – tools through which individuals can practice their selfhood. They allow them to perform "[...] operations on their own bodies and souls, thoughts, conducts, and way of being, so as to transform themselves in order to attain a certain state of happiness, purity, wisdom, perfection, or immortality" (Foucault, 1988, p. 18). Wearables, then, can be said to serve as such tools, enabling individuals, as participants in these structures, to shape and transform themselves in physical and reflexive ways (Lupton, 2016; Lupton, 2013). At the same time, as Dalmer et al. (2024) emphasize, such practices are deeply grounded in and shaped by everything from bodily experiences, emotions, and everyday routines that become intertwined with the personal data generated and interpreted by the self. This second stream thereby critiques the data-centric approaches to the construction of selfhood, imposed by wearables, emphasizing that selfhood is a multifaceted and context-dependent concept: One contingent upon sociocultural communication processes that accumulate, are internalized in autocommunication, and contribute to shaping both the self and the technologies of the self (Lomborg & Frandsen, 2016; Schüll, 2016; Sjöklint, 2014).

Seen from a communication perspective, a third stream combines the overarching ideas of the first two. It describes how wearable tracking technologies can work not simply as means for self-surveillance and control, but for self-exploration, playfulness, and as a form of storytelling about oneself (Lyll, 2024). In relation to the latter, Lohmeier & Pentzold (2025) point out, that "[t]he mnemonic value of such practices is deeply intertwined with identity, community, and the politics of visibility" (p. 2). Self-tracking with wearables

thus operates in dual ways by simultaneously archiving and preserving past behaviors and experiences while also generating new modes of self-knowledge, echoing how Tamm (2019) distinguishes between mnemonic and inventive modes of autocommunication in Lotman's (1990) work. At the same time, this duality is often mirrored in experiences that self-tracking with wearables can create ambivalent forms of self-understanding (Lupton, 2016; Lupton et al., 2018; Salmela et al., 2019; Lomborg et al., 2020; Schüll, 2021; Kressbach, 2024). In a similar vein, Kristensen and Ruckenstein (2018) discuss how "aspects of the self are amplified, while others are reduced or restricted" (p. 3624). This duality resonates with a tension between sensing and seeing that has been identified in the literature on self-tracking and wearables as a place where "body work and knowledge work come together" (Lupton et al., 2018). Here, tracking apps are integrated into bodily behaviors and habits in ways that combine data with lived experience (Clark & Lupton, 2022). Contrasting to ideas that such technologies contribute to the outsourcing of bodily intuition (e.g., Smith & Vonthehoff, 2017), recent studies are beginning to unpack bodily aspects of engaging with self-tracking technologies, such as the role of bodily awareness (Boldi & Rapp, 2022), the interoceptive sense of the human body (Foerster, 2024), and how self-tracking technologies generally work together with the "body as an instrument of knowing" (Algera, 2023, pp. 242-243). In some cases, data generated through wearables can provide insights that make people feel they know themselves and their bodies better, which might then lead to varied feelings, such as anxiety (Lomborg et al., 2020), enthusiasm (Zakariah, Hosany & Cappellini, 2021), and enjoyment (Lupton, 2021). In other cases, technical failures or past personal experiences may make tracking feel useless (Lupton, 2020). Lomborg, Thylstrup and Schwartz (2018) similarly found "an ongoing struggle" in people's internal awareness and external metrics in self-tracking (p. 4595). This stream thus conceives the construction of selfhood as an empirical question with multiple facets and nuances, which calls for people-centric research rooted in everyday experiences and contexts,

beyond theoretical reasoning. Empirical work allows for greater flexibility in the interpretation of how selfhood unfolds in a broader sociocultural process, being constructed in personalized autocommunication with wearables and extending far beyond the transmission of numbers and metrics about bodies, to also encompass individual motivations, bodily experiences and everyday routines and activities in people's lives (Lomborg & Frandsen, 2015).

Autocommunication and decision-making with wearables

The above literatures indicate that selfhood is constructed in communication with the self. Wearable technologies provide users with real-time data about themselves that are, directly or indirectly, included in personal decision-making processes, representing an extra layer of information about themselves. As such, when people use wearables, they communicate with and construct themselves, relating to their devices and data. In doing so, they may also question or reject certain data or even the use of their device. Inspired by Lotman's (1990) concept of autocommunication, Lomborg and Frandsen (2016) conceptualize the use of wearables for self-tracking as a self-communicative phenomenon. They describe how data visualizations "[...] function as a mirror for the self, a means of communicating with the self" (Lomborg & Frandsen, 2015, p. 1021). For instance, people engaging in sleep tracking might ask "how well have I slept the past week?" and might question their data or even device functionalities if there is a mismatch between what they see represented and how they feel. Within this context, Lomborg and Frandsen (2016) draw on the notion of the data double to emphasize the autocommunicative nature of the relationship users have to data visualizations – a relationship based on the "conversion of human bodies and minds into data flows" (Ruckenstein, 2014, p. 68). This relationship with data allows users to reflect on and experiment with themselves.

In Lomborg and Frandsen's (2016) description of how users communicate with themselves as represented in data, the body is depicted primarily as one that delivers data for

autocommunication with self-tracking devices via data visualizations. However, I argue that autocommunication, including that based on data visualizations, is specifically linked to the human body as the primary means of autocommunication, which is further *extended* (McLuhan, 1964) in wearable devices and the data they generate. While bodily extensions in wearables may come to support a person's ongoing autocommunication, self-understanding, and personal decision-making, *autocommunication* itself occurs within the self rather than within the device, and is extended by the *automated communication* (Andrejevic, 2019) from the device rather than replaced by it. In other words, we need to recognize how the body is communicative in and of itself all the time, working as a medium of communication in the first degree (Jensen, 2022). The popularity of using wearables as extensions of the body necessitates a readdressing of basic questions regarding human communication: By being worn or carried and by facilitating automated tracking *about* the body as the primary source for autocommunication, wearables change the conditions under which we as humans use our bodies to communicate. The concept of autocommunication should therefore be expanded to include the use of wearable devices, as they can provide synchronous insights into bodily actions, and enable forms of autocommunication that are influenced both by data and by people's own bodily experiences and personal interpretations.

Although developed without reference to technologies, and in a pre-digital age, Lotman's (1990) concept of autocommunication is helpful in unpacking what autocommunication is, in addition to its relation to wearables. It captures aspects of internal dialogue as humans make sense of themselves in relation to the outside world, working as both the transmitter and recipient of the communicative message; what Lotman (1990, p 26) refers to as "I-I' language". This means that autocommunication amounts to the internal processing of fragments of thoughts, reflections, memories, emotions, and sensations, and is not necessarily articulated as words in the mind. Rather, it is characterized by "the reduction of

words” that “[...] does not form complete sentences but tends to be an unfinalized chain of rhythmical repetitions” (Lotman, 1990, p. 26). As Lotman (1990) puts it, “[...] we are dealing with an increase in information, its transformation, reformulation and with the introduction not of new messages but of new codes, and in this case the addresser and addressee are contained in the same person” (p. 29). Thus, when humans autocommunicate, they engage in internal dialogue and interpretation with themselves whereby meaning is circulated, reproduced, and restructured. As such, “autocommunication is the dominant mode of communication in culture” (Tamm, 2019, p. 6). Tamm (2019) further identifies and distinguishes two spheres of autocommunication across Lotman’s work: mnemonic, which *preserves* information, and inventive, which *generates* new information. Autocommunication thereby helps humans preserve cultural memory and generate new meaning through internal processing and communication.

Lotman’s (1990) theory also implicitly highlights another fundamental aspect of human communication, namely that communication happens *automatically* as part of the way the human body functions. As noted above, in the context of wearables, this communication acquires further *automated* properties, because the availability of digital technology intervenes by mediating and externalizing aspects of human communication, including autocommunication, in ways that would otherwise remain internal and tacit. For instance, wearables might enable humans to compare health metrics over time without having to remember or manually note down certain bodily symptoms. However, wearables do not replace autocommunication, understood as the internal and bodily processes of self-relation. Rather, wearables work through externally automated communicative inputs that may be taken up or ignored by the user’s continuous self-communication. Extending Lotman’s (1990) conceptualization of autocommunication to wearable communication enables an exploration of the complexities of how individuals interpret personal data from wearables and utilize this

information (or not) to make sense, choices, and decisions with or perhaps against their devices. Thus, the concept offers a human-centric perspective on automation by focusing on the automatic and reflexive processes of the human body as a communicative entity in itself. Relatedly, wearables direct attention to the human body as one that also equally constitutes a platform for automated communication, data gathering, and data analysis.

In the following sections, I conceptualize wearables as means of communicating with oneself. I note how wearables facilitate automated communicative inputs about the device, the data, and the body. Borrowing from Lotman's (1990) notion of autocommunication, I then emphasize the combined automatic and extended automated character of the simultaneously bodily and technologically mediated wearable communication. It is automatic because we naturally communicate with and about ourselves, whether intentionally or not. It is automated because wearables pick up signals from our bodies and communicate to us on their own or at least without continuous supervision – and not because aspects of human communication and conduct are taken over or replaced by automated technology. Drawing on Tamm's (2019) account of Lotman's work, I further highlight both the preservative and the generative modes of autocommunication concerning devices, data, and the human body.

Methods and empirical material

The aim of this study is to nuance the understanding of self-tracking as a form of communication with the self and explore how automated communication from wearables are interpreted introspectively and integrated into participants' ongoing autocommunication. To examine autocommunication in the context of the use of wearables, I draw on empirical material from 69 semi-structured photo diaries, and interviews with 25 participants, gathered over one year of fieldwork in Denmark. The data collection process was structured into three waves of photo diaries followed by interviews (beginning, middle, and end). Participants were

asked to photograph a day in their lives, a situation where they had or were using their wearable device, and a situation where they had found it particularly meaningful. The combination of photo diaries and interviews was crucial for capturing instances of autocommunication related to wearables. Photo diaries captured the tacit nature of autocommunication and provided visual insights into everyday experience with wearables. This allowed participants to document moments where they had reflected on or responded to automated communication from their devices. These instances were later discussed more in-depth in the interviews, which were structured to explore participants' introspective engagement with their wearables and the ways they mediate self-reflection. The interviews were semi-structured (Bryman, 2016), allowing participants time to reflect on previously unspoken experiences with wearables.

The sample itself includes 15 women and 10 men aged 20s-60s who use various wearable technologies to track themselves. Twelve participants were recruited for tracking chronic illnesses using consumer apps, ICDs (with and without pacemakers and smartphone applications or other remote monitoring devices attached), continuous glucose monitors (some set up with other devices including smartphone and smartwatch applications to track blood glucose fluctuations), and other public health smartphone apps for reporting, monitoring, and communicating with doctors about their health status. Seven participants tracked general health and well-being, including exercise, sleep, menstruation, stress, and calorie intake, using tracking applications connected to a wide range of wearable devices including smartphones, smartwatches, fitness watches, sensor-based rings, pulse bands, power meters, and bicycle computers. Four participants used devices at work, which included food delivery applications connected to smartphones, and microchips carried internally, ideally to be able to streamline work practices such as printing and opening doors and cabinets to carry out work-related tasks. Finally, two participants both used pregnancy tracking apps and, one of them, Excel sheets that were accessed on the smartphone.

The coding process of the empirical material began descriptively and was later organized into categories (Gibbs, 2012) to identify instances of preservative and generative autocommunication, following Tamm's (2019) framework of mnemonic and inventive modes based on Lotman's (1990) work. The overall focus was on identifying and summarizing instances of self-directed or self-reflexive talk in interview answers or photo diaries descriptions in the interviews. Instances of self-directed or self-reflexive talk were initially confined to single words or short phrases – such as when participant Erik asked himself, “And now what is this all about?”, during the interview (example from the following analysis). However, in the interest of interpreting such instances of autocommunication in their context, the whole paragraph in which they occurred was coded, rather than just the single unit of language. This led to the identification of the three dimensions, the device, the data, and the body, unpacked in the next section. These dimensions emerged inductively from the empirical material, while the theory of autocommunication worked as a conceptual backdrop for further reflection and interpretation, but without predefining the device, data, and body dimensions.

Autocommunication with wearables: Three dimensions

In the interviews, some participants explicitly acknowledged autocommunication with wearables. However, most participants implied that they had inner dialogues about their devices, even if they did not recognize it as communication. In any case, autocommunication with wearables was always with the self, and always about *the device* (tinkering with it), *the data* (carrying, reading, and interpreting the data), and *the body* (listening to bodily signals). Rather than being distinct forms of autocommunication, these dimensions (illustrated in Figure 1, in combination with Lotman's (1990) two modes of autocommunication) represent different themes and types of content in autocommunication when wearables are involved in it.

[**Figure 1.** Illustration of the two modes and three dimensions of autocommunication. See list of figures and images below]

Autocommunicating about the device: Having it do what users want it to do

Users of wearable technologies communicate with themselves about their devices. This type of autocommunication is reflected in the time and effort spent maintaining the setup for tracking, which ensures data generation. As people solve technical issues to keep the system running, they communicate with themselves about their devices. For instance, they may need to edit or add data manually to insure it remains complete, remember to charge devices, or address system errors before tracking can resume. They may also consider exploring other functions of the device to expand its use. In these instances, users act as “user-repairers” and carers who manage things like frequent technological failures (Forlano, 2017, p. 33) and communicate with themselves about it.

Having to spend time setting up or fixing technical issues often disrupts everyday routines. This was common across all forms of tracking in the study, as participants were not keen on dealing with technicalities because they took time. Initially, users struggled to find time to set up devices to do what users wanted them to do, and later, they had to spend additional time resolving the technical issues. Several participants described situations they recalled specifically because of the time it *took* to fix problems with their devices. The ultra-runner Erik (30s, male), for instance, expressed clear frustration with this level of autocommunication concerning having to think about and interpret practical and technical work, including troubleshooting and problem-solving processes triggered by the device:

[...] there are some things that annoy me about it, concerning the fact that at some point you have to keep deleting the routes you have been running, and then if you have a very busy everyday life where at eight o'clock, you can go for a run because then the children

are tucked in and so on – and then it's off because you have one hour because you also have to get home – and then all of a sudden it says that there is no more space. And now what is this all about? Because then you have to go and log in, and that's the thing, you can't just run, because then your mileage won't be the same, so it might be 13-14 kilometers that you don't get in the statistics, I mean, if it's not on Strava, it doesn't exist. [...] Because data means so much, you have to sit down and delete [routes] on the computer, and then it takes 20 minutes before you manage to watch some YouTube videos. So, I've figured it out now, but it was quite annoying. (Erik)

Here, autocommunication involves internally reflecting on and addressing technical issues, making decisions regarding what to do with the device, and then interpreting how it should be practically configured and aligned to fit one's personal needs, preferences, and objectives. Paradoxically, despite automating aspects of human communication, wearables are time-consuming and require mental and manual effort for them to function as intended.

Via tinkering, maintaining, testing, replacing, and fixing devices and data, systems are not only kept up to date by people so that tracking can go on; they are also being personalized. Autocommunication about the device is thereby not just a process where users reflect on sustaining their devices practically, thus maintaining a sense of stability in relation to themselves and their everyday routines (*the self-sustaining mode of autocommunication, e.g., sustaining the habitual engagement with the device through familiar forms of troubleshooting*). But it is also a process through which users implicitly generate new personal and cultural meaning by practically involving themselves with these devices (*the self-inventing mode of autocommunication, e.g., redefining oneself as a particularly committed or technologically competent person*). For instance, the participant Jakob (20s, male), who was frustrated about not being able to use the microchip in his hand, mentioned how he wished there was a “chip community”, where people could “give some life hacks” and have discussions about having a

chip; about “how you use those things, how you can use them to upload data that can be used to make your everyday life easier in one way or another”. But new meaning is also generated when people embrace the premise that metadata needs to be manually added in the app they use because the device cannot tell the difference between walking or playing football, or because it needs help doing calculations like in participant Camilla’s (50s, female) case where her tracking app for diabetes only works if provided with detailed information about, for instance, what her current blood sugar level is, at what level she would like it to be at, and how many carbohydrates she is planning to eat in the next meal: things that she has learnt to calculate herself without the system, because the system needs this information. Autocommunication about the device thus becomes a ritualistic practice that maintains certain meanings associated with the use of wearables – in this case, the implicit understanding that tinkering with technology is a natural part of it. This is also the case when simply structuring charging habits within one’s daily routines, like participant Charlotte (30s, female), who has “found a rhythm” for charging her device. Thus, autocommunication about the device both facilitates tracking and sustains wearable tools in everyday life. Here, tinkering with wearables is a technical and practical activity that intersects with autocommunication. And tinkering involves bringing wearable devices into a communicative form where data outputs can be meaningfully incorporated into autocommunication about the data and the body, as described below.

Autocommunicating about the data: Carrying information mediated by technology

Users of wearable devices also autocommunicate about the data that carry information from and mediated by the device whereby they can ‘see’ or ‘discover’ certain things about themselves and make decisions accordingly. Here, data is valorized as objective and works as an intermediary for communicating with and understanding oneself better, thereby becoming

a “better” version of oneself (Lupton & Smith, 2018). For instance, a user might check data to confirm how well their training went or use notifications and alarms based on tracking data to remind them of achievements or uncompleted activities. In these cases, people expect to see certain things in their data, and their expectations are usually confirmed. Users may even deliberately expose themselves to certain data representations that simply affirm their existing self-image. However, they may also feel a need to “check in” with data (Lomborg, Thylstrup & Schwartz, 2018) to ensure that everything is in order, thereby balancing between modes of sensing and seeing.

For Lene (40s, female), autocommunication about her data confirms that she is a good athlete, and reminds her about past achievements, which creates a positive mindset when she uses her device for training. Even if, during training, she feels more challenged than usual, she can use previous data to remind herself that she ‘knows’ she can do better. If exercise is going well, she simply uses the data as confirmation (*a self-sustaining mode of autocommunication, because it preserves already existing self-knowledge*):

[...] I can use it as a, well, the little devil that sits on my shoulder and says, ‘you can do this’, so, either it supports you or bites your neck and says, ‘pull yourself together because you’re good at this’, ‘you’re just babbling aren’t you?’. So that’s, kind of, one way. Then I can also use it as the person that is like ‘wow, my God, I’m good at this, man, I’m on a roll, man’, ‘this is awesome, isn’t it?’, like, ‘wow, just look at this’. So, that’s the other way, right? (Lene)

However, Lene further elaborates on how she sometimes adjusts her training strategy slightly as she gains new real-time insights from her data (*a self-inventing mode of autocommunication, because it generated new strategies based on the data*). For instance, she describes how she sometimes uses data more actively in decision-making processes during training to tell herself that “now you have to relax a little, otherwise you won’t make it all the way home”. Here, Lene

reproduces an existing perception of herself as an experienced athlete. This experience extends, for instance, to times when she looks at her accumulated results after training.

Although in a different context, similar patterns of confirmation can be seen in participant Jessica's (30s, female) case, where autocommunication about data works to reassure her. Jessica is a heart patient, who has recently had two operations to replace one type of ICD with another, updated ICD, the reason being that the first one had "[...] moved out of place because they [had] installed it incorrectly". The second one, however, had a "technical error in the device" (Jessica), resulting in her getting unmotivated electrical shocks. Although Jessica describes how nothing is actually wrong with her heart, other than an irregular heartbeat, she felt she had to acquire an Apple Watch to be able to track her pulse, read her ECG, and monitor oxygen levels. With her first ICD device, she could not track her data when she was not at the hospital, which made her uncomfortable. Even with the new, updated ICD, which is connected to a Medtronic monitor, placed in her home, she still uses her Apple Watch daily to check in and keep track of her heart rate:

I also think that this is what the Apple Watch does for me. I feel that something is happening in my body. I take a deep breath because it's a feeling – to calm myself down – and then I look at my heart rate on my Apple Watch and when it's decreasing again – and I can see that it's been higher than it was – but when it's going down again, I'm calm about it because then it won't go up again for now. Then I've calmed down and then I continue with my day. I also don't want to be held back because, why? Life is for living, right? Everything else is a waste of time (Jessica)

What Jessica describes is a back-and-forth dialogue between her data and her body to reassure herself that everything is fine. Through this process, she not only sustains a feeling of being in touch with her body – of 'knowing' what is going on, based on what she can see from her data – but she also maintains the identity of being a heart patient. This involves her feeling she needs

to repeatedly check in with her body to find out how it is doing by ‘seeing’ the data to confirm what she had ‘sensed’.

Like Jessica, participant Lea (20s, female) will also check in with her data to confirm bodily feelings and sensations. Lea has been tracking her sleep patterns both before, during, and after pregnancy, and finds that the data helps her verify patterns that she has already noticed about herself: “I can tell when I haven’t slept properly, so I think it’s nice to be able to go in and say ‘ah, that’s why I’ve slept so badly’” (Lea). Such reflections show how Lea feels she can better assess what affects the quality of her sleep. In a similar vein, participant Sidsel (40s, female) manually enters details about her nursing practices into a nursing app – a process that makes her feel calm because the data is used to confirm what she already knows. In both cases, autocommunication about data confirms expectations and promotes feelings of being in control over a body that is implicitly rendered as unpredictable and autonomous. Autocommunication in this context thereby refers to the internal considerations relating to the communicative message from the wearable device; accepting it, resisting it, integrating it, ignoring it, feeling anxious because of it, or using it for other forms of self-reflection. Here, even negative experiences with the device that might lead to rejecting it, are moments of autocommunication because they involve the internal dialogue of what the data mean for the self and how the self decides to act with that additional source of knowledge.

Autocommunicating about the body: A source of information and evidence of ‘how I feel’

Users continuously consult their bodies as parallel, and sometimes primary, sources of evidence. In doing so, they autocommunicate about their bodies. This can lead them to reject data if it contradicts their bodily experience. Similarly, users may find that they do not get “[...] out of their self-tracking devices what they had hoped they would” (Neff & Nafus, 2016, p. 11). In such cases, users prioritize the body over the data as the primary source of evidence for

their feelings. In other instances, data can also reshape bodily communication, and thereby prompt users to view themselves in new ways. In such cases, the evolving relation between bodily sensations and data may lead to new perspectives, practices and meanings, influencing how wearables are used or not used on different contexts.

Participants described how they often felt somehow prepared for what to expect from their data because they had already sensed certain things in their bodies (*a self-sustaining mode of autocommunication, as bodily sensations are clearly recognized*). And these experiences would mostly be confirmed in users' autocommunication about their data. However, several times participants also described the experience of finding a discrepancy between what they had felt and so expected in their data, and what actually was in the data. This made people more aware of their bodies communicating to them irrespective of what their data was telling them. While data were usually seen as objective, people, like participant Alexander (20s, male), generally felt that the body knew better after all:

I think sometimes the watch is quite wrong because [...] sometimes when it says that you are doing really well, your body may just be completely finished. I experienced that not so long ago when my watch just said, 'it's very good – you just have to keep going – training is going great', and my body was like 'I can't do it anymore'.
(Alexander)

This quote brings out the discrepancy that Alexander experiences between the data provided by the device and the actual physical state of his body, which leads him to emphasize his intuitive understanding that his body is a valuable source of evidence in its own right. Participant Christopher (40s, male) describes a similar experience, albeit in a different context. Due to chronic illness, he frequently uses public health apps on his phone, which he always carries with him to keep track of his contacts with health professionals. This includes an app called Medicinkortet ["the medical card"], through which he can communicate with his doctors

about medicine. He describes how Medicinkortet often shows old prescriptions that have not yet been deleted from the app. Consequently, when Christopher recently had surgery, he was medicated incorrectly because the data in his Medicinkortet app had provided the wrong information to his doctor about his bodily condition:

I couldn't get up. My body was so tired. And then I remember informing the doctor about it and then the doctor was like 'yes, I was also wondering why you're taking that muscle relaxant', and I was like 'well, I don't' – 'yes, it's on your medical card', and I said 'well, I took that a very long time ago', [...] and every time I go to the hospital now, I have to tell them everything once again (Christopher)

In Christopher's case, then, bodily sensations become the primary source of evidence. The fact that the data was not taken directly from Christopher's body via his phone, and not manually self-reported, but reported by his doctor via the app, underscores how the body may end up as the one and only source of evidence.

Wishing to sometimes entirely opt out of using wearables was particularly evident for the participants tracking chronic illness, and several participants described how they had initially worked on mentally learning to accept the device as part of their body. For instance, participant Helle (60s, female) found that her Garmin watch provided too much detail about what was going on in her body, which caused her to focus obsessively on feeling her heartbeat. She downgraded to an Apple Watch, which provided her with less data, thereby making it easier for her to enjoy life by, in her case, allowing herself to eat treats and not think about how the body could potentially react negatively to certain habits or lifestyle choices. Ultimately, this made her feel less like a heart patient:

I became totally addicted to it [the Garmin watch, ed.]. I actually felt that when I got up in the morning I thought, 'Well, I'm not dead? No', 'I've slept six hours and then

four’, ‘and my heart rate...’ – and stuff like that. It was put away after a year. I couldn’t control it at all (Helle)

Helle’s quote, like the other respondents, bears witness to struggles of balancing the convenience of using wearables for various forms of personal assistance in daily life, while recognizing the limitations and potential drawbacks of being overly dependent on data. Even when data might simply confirm sensations that are felt in the body and recognized by users, users may eventually decide to move away from involving the automated properties of wearables in making decisions and instead focus more on bodily sensations and intuitions to understand and decide things about themselves (*a self-inventive mode of autocommunication where bodily experiences evolve with bodily data into new perspectives, practices, and patterns of use*). Autocommunication with wearables is thereby always both relational and hierarchical as devices and data must always compete with their users to either complement or be overruled by them. And wearables do not replace moments of autocommunication by providing automated tracking but enter into and participate in an already existing ecology of autocommunication where humans always and automatically also communicate with and about themselves and their bodies.

Concluding discussion: Wearables and the body as a key communicator

The typology developed here, specifies decision-making processes in autocommunication with wearables across three dimensions: devices, data, and bodies. Whereas Foucault’s (1988) “technologies of the self” denote technological tools for asserting “a certain number of operations on [individual’s] own bodies and souls, thoughts, conducts, and way of being” (p. 18), it seems that, in autocommunication with wearables, people assert operations on wearables instead. Contrary to (critiques of) societal and cultural assumptions that it is almost impossible to trust one’s own body, experiences, and senses, as described by Berg (2017), in

autocommunication the body is engaged with and trusted as a valid communicator often trumping the data generated by the wearable devices.

Along the first dimension of autocommunicating about the device, the analysis documented that technology may not be reliable, which leads participants into frequent inner dialogues concerning problem-solving and repair of devices. Along this dimension, device breakages of any kind compel users to spend time focusing their attention, first and foremost, at the functioning of the device at hand. Thus, in any mode of this dimension of autocommunication, decision-making pivots from the intended use of the device to the adjusting of the device itself, thereby highlighting the role of wearables not only as common technological elements in people's lives, but also as material extensions of their bodies in equal need of human care and attention.

Along the second dimension of autocommunicating about the data, the analysis revealed that even if wearable devices do sometimes provide users with valuable information about themselves, users may not necessarily utilize it to make better or different decisions about themselves, instead reverting to and trusting their self-perception. Along this dimension, data are often used to confirm what users are already sensing themselves, and rarely does checking in with one's personal tracking data seem to bring new or surprising insights. Nevertheless, in any mode of this dimension of autocommunication, data points consistently call users to make meaning out of the information they are presented with and cross check this with what they sense in their bodies. This involves several decision-making processes, including mentally processing volumes of data; contemplating their relevance and usefulness, including whether one should act on them; negotiating and holding up what they see in their data against what they subjectively sense and feel: Wearables and the generated data are incorporated into people's inner communication processes – even if it means deciding not to put them into action.

Finally, along the dimension of autocommunicating about the body, the analysis clarified how human intuition, bodily sensations, and personal values, beliefs, judgments, and preferences matter for the decisions people make regarding the use of wearables across different contexts in everyday life. While users do conceive their devices as tools that assist them by providing important and potentially beneficial insights about themselves, they often end up relying, either primarily or at least in parallel, on their own body as a default communicator. Along this dimension, human bodies compete with digital data bodies generated by devices, in ambivalent and contradictory processes where wearables may, on the one hand, make users feel confirmed or enhanced, while on the other hand, add more complexity to their life, to the new habits they might have to settle into, as well as the decisions they have to make (Zimdars, 2021). This suggests that the distinction between the physical body and its digital representation remains relevant. Namely, in any mode of autocommunicating about the body, decision-making is influenced by automatic bodily communication, thereby underscoring the relevance of the human body as a trusted core communicator and decision-maker – and one that is not always easily extended into the automated processes of communication characterizing wearable digital tracking technologies.

The study highlights how wearables enter human communication processes across three dimensions of autocommunication, which shape experience and self-reflections that influence how wearables are engaged with and implemented into daily life as decision-support systems. While technologically mediated data are available from wearables, users often end up relying on bodily communication and their own interpretive agency to arrive at decisions regarding things like their health, their physical activity, or other daily routines. As such, the findings challenge familiar and widespread assumptions that devices can easily and quietly work in the background, automate and take over tasks from the human and, through generating more data, lead to better decision-making. This further specifies the critical role of the human body in

(auto)communication as it relates to wearables. The typology of autocommunication, as it relates to wearables, thus points toward blind spots in the understanding of the communicative work that is an integral part of wearables, repositioning the body as a focal point for further research on digital tracking and emerging automated technologies. Following Lotman (1990), autocommunication involves “an increase in information” (p. 29). With wearables, information is further increased by vast amounts of data, requiring users to engage in additional interpretive processes (Lomborg & Frandsen, 2015). This is also indicated by the analysis, showing how users may both feel enhanced and in control, while at the same time carrying the burdens associated with wearable tracking. Namely, the analysis brings home that extensions of the body in wearables may not necessarily *either* “enhance” and “amplify” (Kristensen, 2022) *or* “restrict” and “reduce” aspects of the self (Kristensen & Ruckenstein, 2018): rather, while users may feel *restricted* by having to continuously maintain their devices, and actively choosing to *reduce* their trust in or use of tracking data from wearables in the context of everyday life, they may, nevertheless, find themselves bodily *enhanced* and generally *amplified* by wearables.

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References

- Algera, E. (2023). Knowing (with) the body: Sensory knowing in contraceptive self-tracking. *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 45(2), 242-258. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9566.13570>
- Andrejevic, M. (2019). *Automated media* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429242595>
- Beer, D. (2019). *The data gaze: Capitalism, power and perception*. Sage Publications. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781526463210>
- Berg, M. (2017). Making sense with sensors: Self-tracking and the temporalities of wellbeing. *Digital Health* 3, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2055207617699767>
- Boldi, A., & Rapp, A. (2022). Quantifying the body: Body image, body awareness and self-tracking technologies. In K. Wac, & S. Wulfovich (Eds.), *Quantifying quality of life: Incorporating daily life into medicine* (pp. 189-207). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-94212-0_9
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social research methods*. Oxford University Press.
- Carey, J. (1989). A cultural approach to communication. In J. Carey (Ed.), *Communication as culture: Essays on media and society* (pp. 13-36). Unwin Hyman.
- Clark, M. & Lupton, D. (2023). The materialities and embodiments of mundane software: Exploring how apps come to matter in everyday life. *Online Information Review*, 47(2), pp. 398-413. <https://doi.org/10.1108/oir-12-2020-0565>
- Dalmer, N., Newman-Griffis, D., Ibrahimi, M., Jia, X., Allhutter, D., Amelang, K., & Jarke, J. (2024). Configuring data subjects. In J. Jarke, & J. Bates (Eds.), *Dialogues in data power: Shifting response-abilities in a datafied world* (pp. 10-30). Bristol University Press. <https://doi.org/10.51952/9781529238327.ch001>

- Foerster, D. (2024). Sensing a heartbeat: A new perspective on self-tracking technologies through the integration of interoception. *Body & Society*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1357034X241245994>
- Forlano, L. (2017). Maintaining, repairing and caring for the multiple subject, *Continent*, 6(1), pp. 30-35. Retrieved June 30, 2024, from https://continentcontinent.cc/content/2-archives/3-issues/5-issue-6-1-2017/7-maintaining-repairing-and-caring-for-the-multiple-subject/277_forlano-maintaining_repairing_and_caring_for_the_multiple_subject.pdf
- Fors, V., Pink, S., Berg, M., & O'Dell, T. (2020). *Imagining personal data: Experiences of self-tracking*. Bloomsbury Academic. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781350051416>
- Foucault, M. (1986). *The care of the self: The history of sexuality*, 3. Pantheon. Retrieved January 9, 2026 from https://monoskop.org/images/1/12/Foucault_Michel_The_History_of_Sexuality_3_The_Care_of_the_Self.pdf
- Foucault, M. (1988). Technologies of the self. In L. Martin, H. Gutman, & P. Hutton (Eds.), *Technologies of the self: A seminar with Michel Foucault* (pp.16-49). London: Tavistock. Retrieved January 9, 2026 from https://monoskop.org/images/0/03/Technologies_of_the_Self_A_Seminar_with_Michel_Foucault.pdf
- Gibbs, G. R. (2007). Thematic coding and categorizing. *Analyzing qualitative data*, 703, 38-56. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781849208574>
- Hepp, A. (2025). Curators of digital futures: The life cycle of pioneer communities. *New Media & Society*, 27(9), 5390-5409. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448241253766>
- Jensen, K. B. (2022). *Media convergence: The three degrees of network, mass, and interpersonal communication* (2nd ed.). Routledge.

- Lohmeier, C., & Pentzold, C. (2025). Unsettling memories: Practice, platforms, and possibilities. Closing reflections on the communicating memory matters collection. *Memory, Mind & Media*, 4, e27, 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1017/mem.2025.10023>
- Lomborg, S. & Frandsen, K. (2016). Self-tracking as communication. *Information, Communication & Society* 19(7), 1015-1027. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2015.1067710>
- Lomborg, S., Thylstrup, N. B., & Schwartz, J. (2018). The temporal flows of self-tracking: Checking in, moving on, staying hooked. *New Media & Society* 20(12), 4590-4607. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/1461444818778542>
- Lomborg, S., Langstrup, H., & Andersen, T. O. (2020). Interpretation as luxury: Heart patients living with data doubt, hope, and anxiety. *Big Data and Society* 7(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951720924436>
- Lotman, I. M. (1990). *Universe of the mind: A semiotic theory of culture*. Indiana University Press. Retrieved January 9, 2026 from https://monoskop.org/images/5/5e/Lotman_Yuri_M_Universe_of_the_Mind_A_Semiotic_Theory_of_Culture_1990.pdf
- Lupton, D. (2013). Understanding the human machine [commentary]. *IEEE Technology and Society Magazine* 32(4), 25-30. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MTS.2013.2286431>
- Lupton, D. (2016). *The quantified self: A sociology of self-tracking*. Polity. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9566.12495>
- Lupton, D. (2020). *Data selves: More-than-human perspectives*. Polity. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24348>
- Lupton, D. (2021). "Sharing is caring:" Australian self-trackers' concepts and practices of personal data sharing and privacy. *Frontiers in Digital Health*, 3. 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdgth.2021.649275>

- Lupton, D., Pink, S., Labond, C. H., & Sumartojo, S. (2018). Personal data contexts, data sense, and self-tracking cycling. *International Journal of Communication*, 12, 647-665. <https://ijoc.org./index.php/ijoc/article/view/5925/2268>
- Lupton, D. & Smith, G. J. (2018). 'A much better person': The agential capacities of self-tracking practices. In D. Lupton (Ed.), *Metric culture: Ontologies of self-tracking practices*. Emerald Publishing Limited (pp. 57-75). <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-78743-289-520181004>
- Lyall, B. (2024). Narratives in numbers: Sociotechnical storytelling with self-tracking. *Memory, Mind & Media*, 3(e1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1017/mem.2023.12>
- Kressbach, M. (2024). *Sensing health: Bodies, data, and digital health technologies*. University of Michigan Press. <https://doi.org/10.3998/mpub.12744203>
- Kristensen, D.B. (2022). The optimised and enhanced self: Experiences of the self and the making of societal values. In M. H. Bruun, A. Wahlberg, R. Douglas-Jones, C. Hasse, K. Hoeyer, D. B. Kristensen, & B. R. Winthereik (Eds.), *The Palgrave handbook of the anthropology of technology* (pp. 585-605). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-7084-8_30
- Kristensen, D. B., & Ruckenstein, M. (2018). Co-evolving with self-tracking technologies. *New Media & Society* 20(10), 3624-3640. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444818755650>
- Krzeminska, A. (2024). Self-optimisation and the technologically mediated self: Balancing self-care and self-control. *Historical Social Research*, 49(3), 77-101. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27331436>
- McLuhan, M. (1964). *Understanding media* (2nd ed.). Routledge.

- Mager, A., & Katzenbach, C. (2021). Future imaginaries in the making and governing of digital technology: Multiple, contested, commodified. *New Media & Society* 23(2), 223-236. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444820929321>
- Markoff, J. (2015). *Machines of loving grace: The quest for common ground between humans and robots*. Harper Collins.
- Meißner, S. (2016). Effects of quantified self beyond self-optimization. In S. Selke (Ed.), *Lifelogging* (pp. 235-248). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-13137-1_13
- Neff, G., & Nafus, D. (2016). *Self-tracking*. The MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/10421.001.0001>
- Nehring, D., & Röcke, A. (2023). Self-optimisation: Conceptual, discursive and historical perspectives, *Current Sociology*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/00113921221146575>
- Olbrich, P., & Witjes, N. (2016). Sociotechnical imaginaries of big data: Commercial satellite imagery and its promise of speed and transparency. In A. Bunnik, A. Cawley, M. Mulqueen, & A. Zwitter (Eds.), *Big data challenges: Society, security, innovation and ethics* (pp. 115-126). Palgrave. https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-349-94885-7_10
- Pantzar, M., & Ruckenstein, M. (2017). Living the metrics: Self-tracking and situated objectivity. *Digital Health* 3, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2055207617712590>
- Pedersen, I., & Iliadis, A. (2020). *Embodied computing: Wearables, implantables, embeddables, ingestibles*. The MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/11564.001.0001>
- Pink, S., Ruckenstein, M., Willim, R., et al. (2016). *Broken data*. Lund: Lund University Publications.

- Rapp, A., & Cena, F. (2016). Personal informatics for everyday life: How users without prior self-tracking experience engage with personal data. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 94, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2016.05.006>
- Ruckenstein, M. (2014). Visualized and interacted life: Personal analytics and engagements with data doubles. *Societies* 4(1), 68-84. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/soc4010068>
- Rieder, G. (2018). Tracing big data imaginaries through public policy: The case of the European Commission. In G. Rieder (Ed.), *The politics and policies of big data* (pp. 89-109). Routledge.
- Ruckenstein, M., & Pantzar, M. (2017). Beyond the quantified self: Thematic exploration of a dataistic paradigm. *New Media & Society* 19(3), 401-418. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444815609081>
- Russell, S. J. (2019). *Human compatible: Artificial intelligence and the problem of control*. London: Allen Lane/Penguin Books.
- Salmela, T., Valtonen, A., & Lupton, D. (2019). The affective circle of harassment and enchantment: Reflections of the OURA ring as an intimate research device. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 23(3), 260-270. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800418801376>
- Sanders, R. (2017). Self-tracking in the digital era: Biopower, patriarchy, and the new biometric body projects. *Body & Society* 23(1), 36-63. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1357034X16660366>
- Schüll, N. D. (2016). Data for life: Wearable technology and the design of self-care. *BioSocieties* 11(3), 317-333. <https://doi.org/10.1057/biosoc.2015.47>
- Schüll, N. D. (2021). Devices and selves: From self-exit to self-fashioning. In H. Geismar, & H. Knox (Eds.), *Digital anthropology* (2ed ed.) (pp. 137-156). Routledge.

- Scott Hansen, S. (2022). Public AI imaginaries: How the debate on artificial intelligence was covered in Danish newspapers and magazines 1956–2021. *Nordicom Review* 43(1), 56-78. <https://doi.org/10.2478/nor-2022-0004>
- Sjöklint, M. (2014). The measurable me: The influence of self-quantification on the online user's decision-making process. *Proceedings of the 2014 ACM International Symposium on Wearable Computers*, 131-137. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2641248.2642737>
- Smith, G. J., & Vonthethoff, B. (2017). Health by numbers? Exploring the practice and experience of datafied health. In D. Lupton (Ed.), *Self-Tracking, health and medicine* (pp. 6-21). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14461242.2016.1196600>
- Tamm, M. (2019). *Juri Lotman – culture, memory and history: Essays in cultural semiotics*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-14710-5>
- Van Den Berg, B. (2012). Pieces of me: On identity and information and communications technology implants. In M. Gasson, E. Kosta, & D. Bowman (Eds.), *Human ICT implants: Technical, legal and ethical considerations* (pp. 159-173). T.M.C. Asser Press. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-6704-870-5_12
- Van Dijck, J. (2014). Datafication, dataism and dataveillance: Big data between scientific paradigm and ideology. *Surveillance & Society* 12(2), 197-208. <https://doi.org/10.24908/ss.v12i2.4776>
- Vigren, M. & Bergroth, H. (2021). Move, eat, sleep, repeat: Living by rhythm with proactive self-tracking technologies. *Nordicom Review* 42(S4). 137-151. <https://doi.org/10.2478/nor-2021-0046>
- Wiedemann, L. (2021). Being on standby: on maintenance work in chronic disease management. *Ephemera* 21(1), 31. Retrieved 9 January 2026 from <https://ephemerajournal.org/sites/default/files/2022-01/21-1Wiedemann.pdf>

Zakariah, A., Hosany, S., & Cappellini, B. (2021). Subjectivities in motion: Dichotomies in consumer engagements with self-tracking technologies. *Computers in Human Behaviour, 118*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2021.106699>

Zimdars, M. (2021). The self-surveillance failures of wearable communication. *Journal of Communication Inquiry, 45*(1), 24-44. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0196859920977113>

